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FACTORS AFFECTING THE ANXIETY LEVEL TOWARDS ONLINE LEARNING AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF EDUCATION STUDENTS IN ISABELA STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

This study was conducted to analyze the factors affecting the level of anxiety of the respondents from the Bachelor of Elementary Education at Isabela State University-Main Campus and its relation to their age, sex, and academic performance. Frequency counts, percentage, Pearson R, T-test, and weighted mean were used to generate results from the acquired quantitative data.

The findings revealed a significant difference in the factors affecting the level of anxiety of the Bachelor of Elementary Education students in Isabela State University-Main Campus towards online learning when grouped according to their sex. Likewise, there is a significant relationship between the factors affecting the levels of anxiety of the students and their age and academic performance.

Keywords: Level of anxiety, Academic performance, Education students, Online Learning

INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has affected many sectors of the whole world. In the Philippines, education is one of the most affected sectors where face-to-face classes have been suspended, and students have undergone online learning to control the spread of the said disease. As an aid for learning, technology plays a vital role in the educational sector.

Despite the possible success of online learning, the sudden shift to exclusive e-learning methods of instruction has produced anxiety and depression symptoms among a significant portion of the students due to the stressful load of work required. Studies have found that online learning has been causing anxiety. (Fawaz and Samaha, 2020).

Stoelker (2021) mentioned that the year 2020 was one of the most anxiety-inducing years in recent memory for college students. Campus closures and the shift to online learning may be one variable that has increased students' anxiety (Johnson, 2020). The same result was found in the study of Fawaz and Samaha (2020) who stated that learning through online platforms has given rise to anxiety disorders among students.

Furthermore, empirical studies have found that students feel that they learn better in physical classrooms than through online education (Bojovic et al., 2020). Baticulon et al. (2021) cited difficulties that the students had encountered like poor internet connection, limited access to gadgets, and lack of study space at home. Rouselle Isla (2020) expressed, "Aside from

the issue of slow and unstable internet that causes videos to freeze and streaming to be disconnected, there may be problems with ambient noises that can be too distracting”.

However, in the study of Lischer et al. (2021), the results showed that female online learners reported higher anxiety compared to male online learners. The findings indicate that women have significantly higher mean anxiety scores when compared to men. However, they observed no significant difference in mean anxiety scores about age.

A related study by Ajmal and Ahmad (2019) found a significant effect of anxiety on academic performance among online learning students of AIOU. While Khest-Majesti et al. (2019) contradicted it, they found out that there was a significantly negative correlation between academic achievement and anxiety.

Therefore, there is a need to conduct this study among the Bachelor of Elementary Education of Isabela State University-Main to determine the factors affecting the level of anxiety that they are facing in the conduct of online classes and if there is an effect on their academic performances, sex, and age.

Statement of the Problem

This study was conducted to determine the factors affecting the levels of anxiety of the Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Isabela State University-Main Campus towards online learning.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of:
 - a. Age; and
 - b. Sex?
2. What is the academic performance of the respondents?
3. What are the factors that affect the level of anxiety of the respondents in online learning in terms of:
 - a. Learner-related factors;
 - b. Mode of learning-related factors; and
 - c. Environment-related factors?
4. What is the difference in the factors that affect the level of anxiety of the respondents when grouped according to sex?
5. What is the relationship between the factors that affect the levels of anxiety of the respondents in online learning when grouped according to:
 - a. Age; and
 - b. Academic Performance?

Scope and Limitation

This study was focused on identifying the factors affecting the levels of anxiety of the Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Isabela State University-Main Campus as well as its relationship to their academic performance for the School Year 2020-2021. The study did not specifically give a direct and tangible solution to the anxiety of the students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational design was used in this study, in which data gathered were recorded, described, interpreted, analyzed, and compared to provide adequate information on the factors affecting the levels of anxiety of the respondents towards online learning. Correlational analysis was used to determine the interaction between the factors affecting the levels of anxiety in online learning and the academic performance of the respondents.

Respondents of the Study

The researchers considered the Bachelor of Elementary Education students of Isabela State University Echague Campus who were enrolled during the First Semester of SY 2020-2021. The sample was determined using stratified random sampling with 5% as the desired margin of error.

Research Instrument

The researchers used the google form questionnaire as an instrument for gathering data. The researchers prepared questionnaires that were distributed to the participants for them to answer online. It contained questions that were relevant to the study. This instrument was used to help researchers gather data easily and safely, especially during the onset of COVID.

Statistical Tools and Treatment

1. Frequency distribution and mean were used to describe the profile, academic performance, and the respondents' perceived factors affecting the level of anxiety in online learning.
2. T-test was also used to determine the difference in the perceived factors affecting the level of anxiety when the respondents were grouped according to their sex.
3. Pearson's R was used to determine the relationship between the factors affecting the level of anxiety in online learning, age, and academic performance of the respondents.

Research Framework

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the summary of the profile of the respondents in terms of sex and age. It can be observed that the majority of the respondents are 21 years old, which accounts for 28.39% of the total sample. Meanwhile, only 1.10% of the sample is 23 years old. The overall mean of the ages of the respondents is 19.85 years old. Among the respondents, 153 or 83.20% of them are female, while 31 or 16.80% are male.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Age and Sex

Variables	Frequency n=184	Percent
Age		
• 17 Years Old	3	1.60
• 18 Years Old	33	17.90
• 19 Years Old	36	19.60
• 20 Years Old	45	24.50
• 21 Years Old	52	28.30
• 22 Years Old	13	7.10
• 23 Years Old	2	1.10
Mean Age = 19.85		
Sex		
• Male	31	16.80
• Female	153	83.20

Academic Performance of the Respondents

Table 2. Academic Performance of the Respondents

Lowest Mark	Highest Mark	Mean	Standard Deviation
5.0	1.25	1.76	0.33

Table 2 shows that the average rating of the respondents is 1.76. It can be observed in the table that the lowest mark is 5.0 and the highest is 1.25. The standard deviation of 0.33 shows that the majority of the respondents' general weighted average is mostly the same, and it is close to its mean of 1.76.

Factors Affecting the Level of Anxiety in Online Learning

Table 3 reveals the factors affecting the levels of anxiety of the respondents on online learning. With a grand mean of 3.37, it can be perceived that the overall level of anxiety of the respondents in terms of learner-related, mode of learning, and environment-related factors that cause anxiety is moderately anxious. This implies that the learner-related, mode of learning-related, and environment-related factors affect the level of anxiety of the students towards online learning.

Table 3. Factors Affecting the Level of Anxiety in Online Learning

Factors of Anxiety in Online Learning	Mean	Qualitative Description
<i>Learner-Related Factor</i>		
1. I feel like I am not intellectually capable of online learning.	3.01	Moderately Anxious
2. I am afraid to give my opinion in my online class due to feelings of embarrassment, self-consciousness, and concern about being judged or viewed negatively by others.	3.40	Moderately Anxious
3. I am shy to express my ideas online.	3.34	Moderately Anxious
4. I find it difficult to motivate myself in starting coursework.	3.04	Moderately Anxious
5. Until now, I find it hard to adapt to the new mode of learning.	3.00	Moderately Anxious
6. I feel like my future is faced with uncertainty due to the sudden switch to online learning.	3.37	Moderately Anxious
7. I usually think that I am being left behind.	3.10	Moderately Anxious
8. I often think that I would have developed more skills if classes were face-to-face.	3.66	Very Anxious
Mean	3.27	Moderately Anxious
<i>Mode of Learning-Related Factor</i>		
9. I feel bothered whenever the internet connection is low.	4.35	Extremely Anxious
10. I feel anxious due to the lack of technology resources (laptop, tablet, computer, mobile phone, etc.) needed for remote learning	3.70	Very Anxious
11. I am afraid of using applications during synchronous classes because I fear that something might go wrong.	3.34	Moderately Anxious
12. I have difficulty learning on my own.	2.98	Moderately Anxious
13. I am not eager in participating in our online classes.	2.82	Moderately Anxious
14. I usually panic before and after a test or activity with a timer.	3.88	Very Anxious
15. Deadlines of activities make me worry too much; I always feel like I am running out of time.	3.70	Very Anxious
16. I get nervous when we are called to recite and to report online.	3.68	Very Anxious
Mean	3.44	Very Anxious
<i>Environment-Related Factor</i>		
17. Our home is not suitable for online learning.	3.16	Moderately Anxious
18. I do not have my own space which is appropriate and suitable for my online classes.	3.04	Moderately Anxious
19. I find it hard to separate my time for classes and requirements because of household chores.	3.58	Very Anxious
20. I have difficulty listening to class discussions because of the noise in our home.	3.51	Very Anxious
21. I find it hard to concentrate during my classes because of too many distractions.	3.62	Very Anxious
22. I am frustrated with the lack of in-person camaraderie, social interaction, and support from my peers.	3.21	Moderately Anxious
23. It is hard to manage my time properly.	3.40	Moderately Anxious
24. The behavior of the people surrounding me at home affects me negatively.	3.01	Moderately Anxious
Mean	3.34	Moderately Anxious
GRAND MEAN	3.37	MODERATELY ANXIOUS

The majority of the respondents' level of anxiety is moderately anxious when it comes to learner-related factors. The respondents experience a moderate level of anxiety when it comes to their intellectual capability for online learning, shyness in expressing their ideas, feelings of embarrassment and fear of being judged when giving their opinions, difficulty in starting coursework, feelings of uncertainty due to the sudden switch to online learning, and thoughts of being left behind. However, the level of anxiety of the respondents is very anxious in the item "I often think that I would have developed more skills if classes were face-to-face." This finding aligns with the findings of Bojovic et al. (2020), where students feel that they learn better in physical classrooms than through online education. This means that students are more likely to be very anxious because of the skills they would have developed if classes were face-to-face.

For the mode of learning-related factors, with a mean of 3.44, the overall level of anxiety of the respondents is very anxious. Specifically, students are very anxious due to the lack of technological resources, approaching deadlines of activities, nervousness when being called for recitation and online reports, and timed during tests or examinations. In line with the findings of Poudel and Subedi (2020), the lack of access to digital resources such as computing devices needed for online learning can increase the level of anxiety of students. Moreover, some students are anxious regarding their online examinations due to the time limit set by some faculty members (Alkandari, 2019) and presenting in front of an audience in a physical classroom or online can create anxiety (Ashkenas, 2014). On the other hand, students are moderately anxious in the matter of the usage of online applications for synchronous classes when they experience difficulty in learning on their own, and when it comes to their eagerness in their online class participation; and students are extremely anxious whenever they are bothered by the low internet connection. This particular result is in line with the study of Baticulon et al. (2020), where they cited poor internet connection as one of the difficulties students encounter in distance learning.

With a grand mean of 3.34, the level of anxiety of the students when it comes to the environment-related factors that cause anxiety is moderately anxious. Students experience a moderate level of anxiety concerning the suitability of their homes for online learning, not having their own space for studying, time management, frustrations with the lack of in-person camaraderie, interaction, and support from peers, and the negative effects of the surrounding people's behavior in their homes. Moreover, students are very anxious when experiencing difficulty separating their time for classes or requirements with their household chores and listening and concentrating on their class discussions because of the noise in their homes and too many distractions. The result of the current study is in line with the study conducted by Rouselle Isla last 2020. Students experience distractions due to the surrounding noises in their homes. Separating home and class activities is challenging because of household chores, and this can cause pressure, stress, and even anxiety to the students and even to the parents. Balancing household chores and attending classes have a huge impact on the anxiety levels of students (Sundarasan, 2020).

Difference in the Level of Anxiety when Respondents are Grouped according to Sex

Table 4 shows the difference in the level of anxiety of the respondents when they are grouped according to sex. As gleaned from the table, when it comes to learner-related factors,

there is no significant difference in the levels of anxiety of the respondents when they are grouped according to sex. It means that both male and female respondents are moderately anxious when it comes to learner-related factors that cause anxiety.

Table 4. Difference in the Level of Anxiety when Respondents are Grouped according to Sex

Factors of Anxiety in Online Learning		Group Means		t-value	p-value
		Male	Female		
LEARNER RELATED FACTORS					
1.	I feel like I am not intellectually capable of online learning.	2.97	3.01	0.27	0.79
2.	I am afraid to give my opinion in my online class due to feelings of embarrassment, self-consciousness, and concern about being judged or viewed negatively by others.	3.16	3.44	1.41	0.16
3.	I am shy to express my ideas online.	3.00	3.41	1.84	0.07
4.	I find it difficult to motivate myself in starting coursework.	3.16	3.01	0.70	0.48
5.	Until now, I find it hard to adapt to the new mode of learning.	2.94	3.01	0.38	0.70
6.	I feel like my future is faced with uncertainty due to the sudden switch to online learning.	3.35	3.37	0.08	0.94
7.	I usually think that I am being left behind.	3.00	3.12	0.54	0.59
8.	I often think that I would have developed more skills if classes were face-to-face.	3.42	3.71	1.19	0.24
MODE OF LEARNING-RELATED FACTORS					
9.	I feel bothered whenever the internet connection is low.	3.29	3.78	0.39	0.70
10.	I feel anxious due to the lack of technology resources (laptop, tablet, computer, mobile phone, etc.) needed for remote learning	3.16	3.37	2.13	0.03
11.	I am afraid of using applications during synchronous classes because I fear that something might go wrong.	3.03	2.97	1.02	0.31
12.	I have difficulty learning on my own.	2.71	2.84	0.28	0.78
13.	I am not eager in participating in our online classes.	3.71	3.91	0.68	0.50
14.	I usually panic before and after a test or activity with a timer.	3.52	3.74	0.86	0.39
15.	Deadlines of activities make me worry too much; I always feel like I am running out of time.	3.45	3.73	1.00	0.32
16.	I get nervous when we are called to recite and to report online.	2.87	3.22	1.25	0.21
ENVIRONMENT-RELATED FACTORS					
17.	Our home is not suitable for online learning.	3.26	3.65	1.43	0.15
18.	I do not have my own space which is appropriate and suitable for my online classes.	3.13	3.59	1.15	0.25
19.	I find it hard to separate my time for classes and requirements because of household chores.	3.45	3.65	1.76	0.08
20.	I have difficulty listening to class discussions because of the noise in our home.	3.06	3.24	2.22	0.03
21.	I find it hard to concentrate during my classes because of too many distractions.	3.16	3.44	0.94	0.35
22.	I am frustrated with the lack of in-person camaraderie, social interaction, and support from my peers.	2.81	3.05	0.83	0.41
23.	It is hard to manage my time properly.	2.97	3.01	1.36	0.17
24.	The behavior of the people surrounding me at home affects me negatively.	3.16	3.44	0.97	0.33

For the mode of learning-related factors, no significant difference can be seen for both male and female respondents when it comes to the low internet connection, fear of using applications during synchronous classes, difficulty in learning on their own, eagerness in online class participation, panicking before and after a timed test or activity, worrying about deadlines and nervousness when called for online recitation or reports. On the other hand, there is a significant difference in the levels of anxiety of the respondents when it comes to feeling anxious due to the lack of technological resources needed for online learning. This is supported by the p-value of 0.03, which means that female respondents with a mean of 3.37 are more anxious than male respondents with a mean of 3.16 when they lack the technological resources needed for online learning.

Under the environment-related factors, there is no significant difference found in the level of anxiety for both male and female respondents. Both males and females are moderately anxious when it comes to the suitability of their homes for online learning, not having their personal space for their online classes, troubles in separating their time for their classes and requirements because of household chores, struggles in concentrating during classes because of too many distractions, frustrations on the lack of in-person camaraderie, social interaction and support from their peers, difficulty in time management and the negative effects of the behavior of the people around them. The table also shows a significant difference in the level of anxiety for the male and female respondents when it comes to the difficulty in listening to class discussions because of the noise in their homes. With a p-value of 0.03, it can be perceived that females with a mean of 3.24 experience a higher level of anxiety than males with a mean of 3.06 due to their difficulty in listening to their class discussions because of the noise in their surroundings. This implies that female respondents tend to feel anxious when they lack the technological resources needed for online learning and have difficulty listening during class discussions compared to male respondents, who are affected by the mode of learning-related and environment-related factors.

While the table shows a significant relationship to the level of anxiety of the students when they are grouped according to sex, the hypothesis is then rejected, particularly in the mode of learning and environment factors.

This particular result of the present study aligns with the study of Khoshaim et al. (2020) who found out that anxiety was highly associated with sex. Also, in the study of Akinsola and Nwajei (2013), female participants reported that they have a higher level of anxiety than males. Conversely, Ajmal and Ahmad (2019) used another set of factors and found that anxiety is slightly higher in males as compared to female students.

Relationship Between the Age, Academic Performance, and the Level of Anxiety of the Respondents in Online Learning

Table 5. Relationship between Age, Academic Performance, and the Level of Anxiety of the Respondents in Online Learning

Factors of Anxiety in Online Learning	Age		Academic Performance	
	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value
LEARNER RELATED FACTORS				
1. I feel like I am not intellectually capable of online learning.	0.13	0.07	-0.01	0.85
2. I am afraid to give my opinion in my online class due to feelings of embarrassment, self-consciousness, and concern about being judged or viewed negatively by others.	0.03	0.71	0.11	0.13
3. I am shy to express my ideas online.	0.03	0.72	-0.14	0.05
4. I find it difficult to motivate myself in starting coursework.	0.10	0.19	0.07	0.34
5. Until now, I find it hard to adapt to the new mode of learning.	0.03	0.66	-0.20	0.01
6. I feel like my future is faced with uncertainty due to the sudden switch to online learning.	0.16	0.04	0.01	0.99
7. I usually think that I am being left behind.	0.04	0.59	-0.03	0.72
8. I often think that I would have developed more skills if classes were face-to-face.	0.14	0.05	0.03	0.69
MODE OF LEARNING-RELATED FACTORS				
9. I feel bothered whenever the internet connection is low.	0.03	0.74	0.08	0.27
10. I feel anxious due to the lack of technology resources (laptop, tablet, computer, mobile phone, etc.) needed for remote learning	0.13	0.08	-0.04	0.62
11. I am afraid of using applications during synchronous classes because I fear that something might go wrong.	0.09	0.22	-0.04	0.60
12. I have difficulty learning on my own.	-0.01	0.98	-0.08	0.26
13. I am not eager in participating in our online classes.	0.04	0.57	-0.03	0.69
14. I usually panic before and after a test or activity with a timer.	0.02	0.75	0.01	0.97
15. Deadlines of activities make me worry too much; I always feel like I am running out of time.	0.11	0.15	-0.06	0.44
16. I get nervous when we are called to recite and to report online.	0.02	0.79	0.09	0.22

ENVIRONMENT-RELATED FACTORS

17. Our home is not suitable for online learning.	0.17	0.03	-0.11	0.16
18. I do not have my own space which is appropriate and suitable for my online classes.	0.12	0.11	-0.12	0.10
19. I find it hard to separate my time for classes and requirements because of household chores.	0.08	0.30	-0.08	0.26
20. I have difficulty listening to class discussions because of the noise in our home.	0.08	0.29	-0.13	0.09
21. I find it hard to concentrate during my classes because of too many distractions.	0.06	0.45	-0.11	0.15
22. I am frustrated with the lack of in-person camaraderie, social interaction, and support from my peers.	0.13	0.09	-0.11	0.15
23. It is hard to manage my time properly.	-0.01	0.86	-0.13	0.07
24. The behavior of the people surrounding me at home affects me negatively.	0.17	0.02	0.04	0.62

Table 5 explains the relationship between the age and the level of anxiety of the respondents in online learning. Also, the relationship between the academic performance and the level of anxiety of the respondents in online learning is presented.

Age and Level of Anxiety in Online Learning

As gleaned from the table, there is no significant relationship between the age and the level of anxiety of the respondents when it comes to their intellectual capability for online learning, being shy to express their ideas online, self-conscious and embarrassed when giving their own opinions online, being left behind, difficulty in starting coursework, and adapting to the new mode of learning. However, there is a significant relationship between the age of the respondents when they have feelings of uncertainty for their future because of the sudden switch to online learning and when they think that they would have developed more skills if classes were online. With a p-value of 0.04 and an r-value of 0.16, it can be observed that older respondents tend to be more anxious when it comes to the uncertainty of their future due to the sudden switch to online learning. Moreover, a p-value of 0.05 and an r-value of 0.14 indicate that older respondents are more anxious when they think they would have developed more skills if face-to-face classes.

Under the mode of learning-related factors, no significant relationship can be found between the respondents' age and level of anxiety about online learning.

For the environment-related factors, there is a significant relationship between the age of the respondents and their level of anxiety. With a p-value of 0.03 and an r-value of 0.17, compared to the younger respondents, older respondents appear to be more anxious because their homes are not suitable for online learning. In addition, older respondents are more anxious than the younger respondents when it comes to the negative effects brought by the behavior of the people surrounding them at home; this is supported by the p-value of 0.02 and r-value of 0.17. The implication of these findings reveals that learner-related factors and environment-related factors affect the level of anxiety of the respondents of older respondents who are more anxious than younger respondents.

The result of the present study contradicts the study of Khest-Masjedi et al. (2019) who found out that there is no significant relationship between depression and the age. Also, Lischer et al. (2021) observed no significant relationship in mean scores with regard to age.

Academic Performance and Level of Anxiety in Online Learning

Table 5 also explains the relationship between the academic performance of the students and the factors affecting their level of anxiety in online learning. It can be inferred

from the table that the levels of anxiety of the respondents do not entirely affect their academic performance. For the learner-related factors, very weak relationships can be seen between the levels of anxiety of the respondents to their intellectual capabilities for online learning, fear of voicing out their opinions due to feelings of embarrassment, difficulty in motivating themselves in starting coursework, feelings of uncertainty for their future due to the sudden switch to online learning, being left behind and having more developed skills if classes were face-to-face. However, there is a significant relationship between the academic performance of the students and their level of anxiety when it comes to their shyness in expressing their ideas online and their adaptability to the new mode of learning. With an r-value of -0.14, it can be inferred that the respondents' academic performance is affected by their level of anxiety when they are shy to express their ideas online. The result of this study aligns with the previous study conducted by Kasper (2012), where he found that shy students are likely to be avoiding educational situations, which results in not being able to reach their full potential in the academic setting. Hence, their academic performance is being affected. Furthermore, the r-value of -0.20 in the respondent's difficulty in adapting to the new mode of learning tells us that the academic performance of the respondents is affected by their level of anxiety. Syokwaa et al. (2020) found a correlation between anxiety levels and academic achievement. High anxiety levels have a negative impact on the quality of academic results recorded by students.

In the mode of learning-related and environment-related factors causing anxiety, the majority of the student's academic performance is not affected by their levels of anxiety. Very weak relationships can be seen, which only means that the respondent's level of anxiety does not affect their academic performance when it comes to mode of learning-related and environment-related factors that cause anxiety. It can be inferred that the academic performance of the respondent's level of anxiety is affected by the learner-related factor when they are shy about expressing their ideas online and have difficulty adapting to the new mode of learning.

While the table shows that there is a significant relationship in the level of anxiety of the students when they are grouped according to academic performance, the null hypothesis is then rejected, particularly in the learner-related factor.

The result of the present study aligns with the study of Ajmal and Ahmad (2019), in which a significant effect of anxiety on the academic performance of distance learners was found. However, it contradicted the study of Khest-Masjedi et al. (2019) who found a negative correlation between academic achievement and anxiety.

Conclusion

Based on the findings presented, the researchers concluded that the level of anxiety of the selected respondents from the Bachelor of Elementary Education students of Isabela State University-Main Campus was moderate when it comes to learner-related and environmental-related factors. Furthermore, the respondents were very anxious in terms of the mode of learning-related factors.

When grouped according to profiles, there was a significant difference in the level of anxiety in online learning and the sex of the respondents.

It can also be concluded that there was a significant relationship between the level of anxiety in online learning and the age of the respondents. It showed that older respondents were more anxious than younger ones under learner-related factors. Moreover, for the environment-related factors, older respondents appeared to be more anxious because their homes are not suitable for online learning and when it comes to negative effects brought by the behavior of the people surrounding them at home.

Lastly, there was a significant relationship between the level of anxiety in online learning and the academic performance of the respondents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are recommended:

1. The instrument used in this study has to undergo validation and reliability testing.
2. Parents and teachers should provide resources that support a positive learning environment for students, like technological resources, internet access, and space for the learning environment. A positive environment can help students to adapt to the new normal.
3. Students should politely talk to the teachers if they have a poor internet connection. On the other hand, teachers should also be considerate to the students who have a slow internet connection. They may provide downloadable files or recorded videos of the lesson, which students can use even offline.
4. Barangay and SK officials should propose a program for students to use laptops at the barangay hall intended for online learning. They may coordinate with teachers and conduct a program or a symposium on how to cope with anxiety, especially in an online learning environment.
5. Teachers should adjust or add more time on giving tests or activities.
6. Students may make a journal or their daily schedule to manage their time wisely and separate the time for household chores, requirements, synchronous classes, and other activities.
7. Teachers may establish information desks well to reach out to the students and to guide them with all necessary information.

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